

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Addressing the special educational needs and disabilities (SEND) assessment and support crisis

Target Audience: Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based approach to addressing the special needs and disabilities (SEND) assessment and support crisis

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Key Evidence Based Messages

- **There is a high prevalence of special educational needs and disabilities (SEND), but the SEND system is in crisis.** Around 40% of 5-16 year olds will be diagnosed with a SEND at some point. But significant delays in identifying needs, long waiting times, a lack of provision, exacerbated by a postcode lottery, and a severe funding crisis all mean children and families suffer.
- **The lack of provision has a devastating impact on academic, social and emotional development.** Children with SEND experience poorer education outcomes, higher rates of exclusion and are more likely to be NEET (not in education, employment or training)
- **Children from the most deprived areas are particularly at risk from the crisis in provision.** They are 18.5 percentage points behind children from the least deprived areas on the Early Years Foundation Stage (EYFS) profile.
- **National level focus:**
 - Use holistic child development measures to identify children.
 - Improve and extend training opportunities for professionals and families on SEND.
 - Join up services (education, health, social care) to enable earlier identification and provision of support.
- **Local level focus:**
 - Join up education health and social care services; improve assessment processes to support early identification and support, develop local training and Continuing Professional Development (CPD) support; provide tailored mental health support and develop robust monitoring and evaluation.

The Problem: There is a crisis in SEND assessment and support. The system is failing children, families, schools and local authorities and the poorest children and families are hardest hit.

1.5 million pupils in England have SEND - 40% of children at some point between ages 5-16 are identified as having SEND.

SEND Children are more likely to have a probable mental health disorder. In 2021 reported rates were 57% for SEND children and 13% for non SEND

By the end of secondary school, the attainment gap between children with no identified SEND and children with an Education, Health and Care Plan is 3.5 years. 32% of children with SEND are persistently absent from school. They are three times more likely to be excluded and three times more likely to be NEET at 16-17 years of age.

Only half of EHC plans were produced in the 20 week statutory limit. In some council areas rates could fall below 10%. In one West Yorkshire local authority the average wait for an ADHD assessment for 19-25 year olds was 4 years.

The current system is in financial crisis. A recent National Audit Office report (2024) argues the system is financially unsustainable. In Oct 2024, DfE estimated a £4.6 billion deficit in dedicated schools grant by the end of 2025-2026.

What you can do at a local level

- **Join up education, health and social care services.** This enables sharing of information, earlier identification of need and better support.
- **Improve assessment processes and early identification tools. Streamline the process. The key is a holistic approach to assessment and support. This helps with early identification of problems, ensures access to services and helps to stop children getting lost in the system.**
- **Enhance training and CPD for teachers, support staff and administrative personnel. Focus on early identification, understanding diverse needs and effective support strategies, include professionals and parents.**
- **Provide advice, information and guidance services for parents and caregivers so that they can navigate the SEND system.**
- **Develop tailored mental health support for children with SEND. Children with SEND have reported higher rates of mental health disorders compared to children without a SEND.**
- **Establish robust monitoring and evaluation to regularly review policy and practice, identify what works and adjust policy.**
- **Develop the kinds of programmes highlighted below.**

Approaches trialled in prac-

Example	Approach	Impact
Hilltop and Forest View School	Integrates academic, therapeutic, and life skills education. A bespoke curriculum is tailored to achieve EHC plan outcomes, alongside personal, social, and health education (PSHE) objectives, and preparation for adulthood initiatives. The school works closely in partnership with support services and families and has a dedicated family support team.	Improved academic, social and emotional achievement.
Tees Valley	A service which aims to promote children's communication and language development, wellbeing, and involvement through the provision of high-quality outdoor learning and play	Improved children's wellbeing and involvement scores.
Dixons Academies Trust	Describes its approach as "mountain rescue": the ethos is to enable children to climb the mountain of schooling. Adopts a multi-disciplinary approach, utilising shared spaces, combined resources, and collaborative leadership to streamline provision and meet the needs of all children holistically. School pastoral staff work closely alongside the school SENDCo, "Mountain Rescue" mentors, and other professionals who come into school (e.g., educational psychologists, psychotherapists)	Optimises the flows of information, resources, and support to protect every students' entitlement to the best education.
The Bradford Alternative Provision Academy - Alternative Provision Specialist Taskforce (APST)	The APST takes a multidisciplinary approach to identifying and supporting children with SEND. The taskforce includes a mental health therapist and nurse, a speech and language therapist, youth workers, a justice worker, a post-16 coach, a family support worker, and an enrichment coordinator, building a robust support system for the students	Increased engagement, retention, achievement and progression. In its first year, attendance for APST students was 71%, compared to 64% for the wider pupil cohort at BAPA. 92% of Year 11 students who engaged with APST achieved a GCSE qualification in both English and Maths, compared to only 68% of the whole of the BAPA cohort.

Example	Approach	Impact
The Morecombe Bay Curriculum Project	Developed place-based curricula that help young people understand the local environment and the ecological challenges we face, and gain the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable practices. A teacher acts as SEND advisor adapting curriculum and developing engagement activities.	Development of accessible and engaging curricula for the inclusion of all pupils.
Early Identification Tools	There are a range of tools being developed and trialed including Electronic Development and Support Tool, FUNMOVES, Working Memory Screening Questionnaire. They all aim to support teachers in early identification and assessment of needs.	Early identification of needs, earlier intervention and better targeting and tailoring of support.

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